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Impact Factor: 3.43

Cite this paper as : Satya Ranjan Doley (2017), “A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON MFI-BANK LINKAGE AND SHG-BANK LINKAGE PROGRAMME” International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management, ISSN: 2348 –3954 (online) ISSN: 2349 –2546 (print), Volume 5,(Issue 6, Jun-2017), pp 64-71,

A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON MFI-BANK LINKAGE AND SHG-BANK LINKAGE PROGRAMME

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ABSTRACT

The banks are offering financial assistance to MFIs and SHGs in the form of loan. These loans are repayable to banks after specified period of time. The study was undertaken to study growth rate of loan disbursement between MFI-Bank Linkage and SHG-Bank Linkage in India and to study growth rate of loan outstanding between MFI-Bank Linkage and SHG-Bank Linkage in India. The present study is based on secondary sources of data. The study makes use of statistics such as arithmetic mean, standard deviation, co-efficient of variation and Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) to analyze the data. Non parametric test viz. Man-Whitney U test has been used to draw inference on the framed hypotheses. It was observed that the CAGR of amount of loan disbursed to MFI during the period from 2007-08 to 2015-16 is 33.56 percent while the CAGR of total amount of loan disbursed to SHGs in India for the same period is 17.33 percent. The hypothesis testing proves that there is no significant difference in the growth rate of loan disbursement between MFI- Bank linkage and SHG-Bank Linkage program. The CAGR of amount of loan outstanding against MFI during the period from 2007-08 to 2015-16 is 32.07 percent while the CAGR of total amount of loan outstanding against SHGs in India for the period is 14.41 percent. The hypothesis testing proves that there is no significant difference in the growth rate of loan outstanding between MFI- Bank linkage and SHG-Bank Linkage program.

Keywords: MFIs, SHGs, SHG-Bank Linkage programme, CAGR, Man-whitney U test.

Introduction:-

Microfinance Industry plays a pivotal role in developing country. Microfinance refers to the entire range of financial services such as savings, money transfer, insurance, production and investment credit as also housing finance and includes the need for skill up gradation and entrepreneurial development that would enable them to overcome poverty. Microfinance provides credit support in small doses along with training and other related services to people who are resource-poor but who are able to undertake economic activities (Suguna, B. 2006).

The Micro finance Institutions (MFIs) have emerged to fulfill the gap that conventional financial institutions could not cover all people. It can be broadly defined as institutions other than banks that are engaged in providing financial services to the poor (Jindal, Krishan, 2008).” Various types of MFIs can be formed viz. NGO-MFIs, Non-profit Companies as MFIs, Mutual Benefit MFIs and For Profit MFIs etc. MFIs have the facility of getting credit from the banks.

The Self Help Groups (SHGs) are voluntary associations of people formed to attain a collective goal. People who are homogeneous with respect to social background, heritage, caste or traditional occupation come together for a common cause to raise and manage resources for the benefit of the group members (Jerinabi, U. 2006). These are grouped and monitored primarily under three models based on their linkage with the supporting

institution namely- Model-I: bank promoted; Model-II: government agency-promoted; Model-III: NGO-promoted.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Bright, A. et al. (2011) conducted a study titled A study on the annual micro credit plan of banks and financial institutions in kanyakumari district. The objective of the study was a) to study the annual credit plans of banks and financial institutions operating in kanyakumari district during 2005 to 2009 for micro credit, b) to study the growth pattern of micro credit offered during 2005-2009 by banks and financial institutions operating in kanyakumari district. Only secondary data was used –Annual credit plan published by lead bank office in kanyakumari district. The study came to a conclusion that the growth pattern of micro credit offered in the district is found to be negative in most of the schemes and plans of micro credit. Singha, R.K.P.G. (2011) did a research study on Microfinance in India: A critical Analysis of SHG-bank linkages. The paper examines the SHG-bank linkage in India and problems of micro finance. The paper came to conclusion that micro finance is an important component for socio economic upliftment of rural poor as they can not access to the formal credit from the financial institution due to many known and unknown reasons. Apart from these, cumbersome procedures and risk perceptions of the banks left a gap in serving the credit needs of the rural poor. The rural poor continue to depend on informal sources of credit. Micro finance enables the poor to be thrifty and helps them in availing the credit and other financial services for improving their income and living standards. Microfinance and micro enterprises and SHGs are the core requirement for the upgradation of economically backward communities especially women folk. Anuradha, PS and Ganesan, G. (2010) in their paper concluded that micro finance is a powerful tool for sustainable development and helps in attaining inclusive growth by creating employment, reducing gender and geography differences which lead to the expansion of economy, thereby contributing to the growth of the economy. Sudalaimuthu, S. et.al (2010) in their paper concluded that microfinance programme has become an important tool to eradicate poverty in India. It is gathering momentum to become a major force in India. Self Help Group model with bank lending to groups of poor women without collateral has become an accepted part of rural finance. Panigrahi, S. (2010) in his paper concluded that many other linkage programme with MFIs have shown the path forward for accessing mainstream finance exclusively from the formal banking sector for microfinance. SBLP facilitates financial deepening and smoothing of credit services by accessing mainstream banking resources.

It has been observed that there is enough review of literature in the field of micro finance. But there is a few comparative study of linkage programme made in this area. Considering this gap and the need of the study, the researcher has taken up the present study.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The players of microfinance need financial assistance from the banks in order to run this industry. It is considered as the priority sector of the banks. Considering its importance, the banks are offering financial assistance to MFIs and SHGs in the form of loan. These loans are repayable to banks after specified period of time. The present study focuses on the MFI- Bank linkage and SHG- bank linkage programme of India.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objective of the paper is to study growth rate of loan disbursement between MFI-Bank Linkage and SHG-Bank Linkage in India (2) to study growth rate of loan outstanding between MFI-Bank Linkage and SHG-Bank Linkage in India.

HYPOTHESES

Ho1: There is significant association between the growth rate of loan disbursement between MFI-Credit Linkage and SHG-Credit Linkage in India during the study period.

Ho2: There is significant association between the growth rate of loan outstanding between MFI-credit Linkage and SHG-Credit Linkage in India during the study period.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study is descriptive in nature. It based on secondary sources of data collected from the status of microfinance, NABARD Report. The other sources of relevant secondary data are also consulted to have idea about theoretical framework and review literature. The sample size of the study is for the period of eight years. The study makes use of descriptive statistics such as arithmetic mean, standard deviation, co-efficient of variation to analyze the data. Moreover, Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) is used to find the average growth rate during the study period. Non parametric test viz. Man-Whitney U test has been used to draw inference on the framed hypotheses. This test is suitable to infer data below the sample size of ten in any study. The present study covers the period of eight years from 2007-08 to 2015-16 known as reference period of the study.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study covers two important linkage programs in India viz. MFI-Bank linkage program and SHG-Bank Linkage program. It mainly focuses on the loan disbursed to MFI and SHGs and loan outstanding of them under the bank linkage program.

DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS

Under both linkage programs, banks provide credit to the MFIs and SHGs which also acts as micro finance service providers. The study discusses the number of MFIs and SHGs at national level getting bank loan, loan disbursed to them, their number of outstanding loan against them and outstanding loan against them for the period of eight years.

Table 1: Growth Rate of MFIs and SHGs under Bank Linkage Program (Loan disbursed)

Years	MFI-Bank Linkage		SHG-Bank Linkage	
	No. of MFI	Annual Growth	No. of SHGs (lakh)	Annual Growth
07-08	518		12.28	
08-09	581	12.2	16.10	(31.1%)
09-10	691	18.9	15.87	(-1.4%)
10-11	471	-39.5	11.96	(-24.6%)
11-12	465	-1.3	11.48	(-4%)
12-13	426	-8.4	12.20	(6.3%)
13-14	545	27.9	13.66	(12.0%)
14-15	589	8.1	16.26	(19.0%)
15-16	647	9.8	18.32	(12.7%)
AM	526.7		14.24	
SD	106.9		2.45	
CV	20.30		17.21	
CAGR	6.84		4.54	

Source: Status of microfinance, NABARD Report of various years

The growth rate of number of MFIs which obtained loan from Bank in India in 2008- 2009 is 12.2 percent in 2008-2009 which increases to 18.9 percent in next year (Table 1). There is negative growth of MFIs (-39.5 percent) in 2010-2011 those which availed loan. In the next year, it was found to be again negative growth (-1.3

percent) which goes up to -8.4 percent in 2012-2013. Then it increased to 27.9 percent in 2013-2014 which declines to 8.1 percent in 2014-2015. In succeeding year, it increased to 9.8 percent. The mean value of total number of MFIs who has obtained loan for the period from 2006-2007 to 2015-2016 is 526.7 with SD 106.9 and CV 20.30. The CAGR of total number of MFI for the same period is 6.84 percent.

The growth rate of total number of SHGs obtaining loan from bank in India in 2008-2009 is 31.1 percent. It goes down to -1.4 percent in 2009-2010 which declines further to -24.6 percent in next year. The decrease in growth is negative (- 4 percent) in 2011- 2012. It goes up during next three years. It declines to 12.67 percent in 2015-2016. The mean value of total number of SHGs for the period from 2007-2008 to 2015-2016 is 14.24 with SD 2.45 and CV 17.21. The CAGR of total number of SHGs for the similar period is 4.54 percent.

Table 2: Growth Rate of loan disbursed under Bank Linkage Program

Years	MFI-Bank Linkage		SHG-Bank Linkage	
	Amount of loan (Rs. in crore)	Annual Growth	Amount of loan (Rs.crore)	Annual Growth
07-08	1970.15		8849.26	
08-09	3732.33	89.4	12253.51	(38.5%)
09-10	8062.74	116	14453.30	(17.9%)
10-11	8448.96	4.79	14547.73	(0.01%)
11-12	5205.29	-38.39	16534.77	(13.7%)
12-13	7839.51	50.6	20585.36	(24.5%)
13-14	10282.49	31.16	24017.36	(16.7%)
14-15	15190.13	47.73	27582.31	(14.8%)
15-16	20795.57	36.90	37286.90	(35.2%)
AM	8267.87		19567.83	
SD	6050.08		8859.86	
CV	73.18		45.28	
CAGR	33.56		17.33	

The growth rate of amount of bank loan disbursed to MFIs of India in 2008-2009 is 89.4 percent (Table 2) which increases in next year 2009 -2010. It declines to 4.79 percent in 2010-2011 which becomes negative (- 38.39%) in 2011-2012. It increases to 50.6 percent in 2012-2013. In 2013-2014, it declines to 31.16 percent and then rises to 47.73 percent in next year. It goes down to 36.90 percent in 2015-2016. The mean value of amount of bank loan disbursed to MFIs for the period 2006-2007 to 2015-2016 is 8267.87 with SD 6050.08 and CV 73.18. The CAGR of amount of loan disbursed to MFI during the same period is 33.56 percent. This shows that there has been an average growth in the amount of loan obtained.

The growth rate of total amount of loan disbursement to SHGs of India in 2008-2009 is 38.5 percent. It goes down to 17.9 percent during 2009-2010 which continues to decrease to 0.01 percent in 2010-2011. In succeeding year, it increases to 13.7 percent which continues to go up to 24.5 percent during 2012- 2013. It declines during next two years which rises to 35.2 percent in 2015-2016. The mean value of loan disbursement to SHGs during the period from 2007-2008 to 2015-2016 is 19567.83 with SD 8859.86 and CV 45.28. The CAGR of total amount of loan disbursement in India for the period is 17.33 percent.

Testing of Hypothesis

Table 3: Man-Whitney U Test of loan disbursed of MFI- Bank linkage and Bank Linkage

Years	MFI-Bank Linkage		SHG-Bank Linkage	
	Growth	Rank	Growth	Rank
08-09	89.4	15	38.5	12
09-10	116	16	17.9	07
10-11	4.79	03	0.01	02
11-12	-38.39	01	13.7	04
12-13	50.6	14	24.5	08
13-14	31.16	09	16.7	06
14-15	47.73	13	14.8	05
15-16	36.90	11	35.2	10
Sum of rank order		82		54
No. of Data		08		08
U value	18			
Z value	1.565			

Inference on Hypothesis

The calculated value of U is 18 which is higher than critical value of U (2) at significance level of 0.05 (Table 3).

Table 4: Growth Rate of MFIs and SHGs under Bank Linkage Program (Loan Outstanding)

Years	MFI-Bank Linkage		SHG-Bank Linkage	
	No. of MFIs	Annual Growth	No. of SHGs	Annual Growth
07-08	1109		36.26	
08-09	1915	72.7	42.24	(16.5%)
09-10	1513	21.0	48.51	(14.8%)
10-11	2315	39.5	47.87	(-1.3%)
11-12	1960	-15.3	43.54	(-9.0%)
12-13	2042	4.2	44.51	(2.2%)
13-14	2422	18.6	41.97	(-5.7%)
14-15	4662	92.5	44.68	(6.5%)
15-16	2020	- 56.7	46.73	(4.6%)
AM	2050.80		44.03	
SD	1079.21		3.72	
CV	52.62		8.49	
CAGR	13.89		2.86	

Source: Status of microfinance, NABARD Report of various years.

It can be said that the difference in the growth rate of loan disbursement between MFI- Bank linkage and SHG-Bank Linkage program is not significant at $p = 0.05$. It is further confirmed by calculating Z score (1.565) which

is less than 1.96. There is no significant difference in the growth rate of loan disbursement between MFI- Bank linkage and SHG-Bank Linkage program is upheld.

The growth rate of total number of MFIs with outstanding loan in India in 2008-2009 is 72.7 percent which declines during next year 2009-2010 (Table 4). It goes up to 39.5 percent in 2010-2011 which becomes negative (-15.3 percent) in 2011-2012. It rises to 4.2 percent 2012-2013 which goes up during next two years. In 2015-2016, it becomes negative (- 56.7 percent). The mean value of total number of MFIs for the period from 2006-2007 to 2015-2016 is 2050.80 with SD 1079.21 and CV 52.62. The CAGR of total number of MFI with loan outstanding for same the period is 13.89 percent.

The growth rate of total number of SHGs with outstanding loan in India during the year 2008-2009 is 16.5 percent. It goes down in three consecutive years again it increases to 2.2 percent in 2012-2013. It becomes negative -5.7 percent in 2013-2014 which increases to 6.5 percent in 2014-2015. In next year 2015-2016, it decreases to 4.6 percent. The mean value of total number of SHGs for the period from 2007-2008 to 2015-2016 is 44.03 with SD 3.72 and CV 8.49. The CAGR of total number of SHGs in India during entire period is 2.86 percent.

Table 5: Growth of loan outstanding under Bank Linkage Program (Rs. crore)

Years	MFI-Bank Linkage		SHG-Bank Linkage	
	Amount	Annual Growth	Amount	Annual growth
07-08	2748.84		16999.91	
08-09	5009.09	82.2	22679.84	33.4
09-10	10147.54	102.6	28038.28	23.6
10-11	13730.62	35.3	31221.17	11.4
11-12	11450.35	-16.6	36340.00	16.4
12-13	14425.84	26.0	39375.30	8.4
13-14	16517.43	14.50	42927.52	9.02
14-15	22500.46	36.22	51545.46	20.06
15-16	25580.84	13.69	57119.23	10.81
AM	12369.55		36249.63	
SD	7953.29		13092.35	
CV	64.30		36.12	
CAGR	32.07		14.41	

Source: Status of microfinance, NABARD Report of various years.

The growth rate of loan outstanding against MFIs in India (2008-2009) is 82.2 percent which increase in next year (Table 5). The growth rate came down during next two years. It increases to 26 percent in 2012-2013. In 2013-2014, it again declined to 14.50 percent and then rises to 36.22 percent in next year. It goes down to 13.69 percent in 2015-2016. The mean value of outstanding against for MFIs from 2006-2007 to 2015-2016 is 12369.55 with SD 7953.29 and CV 64.30. The CAGR of total amount of loan outstanding against MFI for the same period is 32.07 percent. It has been observed that the role of MFIs in financing is significant over the years although it is not showing continuous growth.

The growth rate of amount of outstanding loan (2008-2009) against SHGs in is 33.4 percent. It declines during next two years which rises to 16.4 percent during 2011-2012. It declined to 8.4% in 2012-2013 which goes up

during next two years. It decreases to 10.81 percent in 2015-2016. The mean value of total amount of loan outstanding against SHGs for the period from 2007-2008 to 2015-2016 is 36249.63 with SD 13092.35 and CV 36.12. The CAGR of total amount of outstanding loan in India during the study period is 14.41 percent.

Testing of Hypothesis

Table 6: Man-Whitney U Test of Growth of loan outstanding under Bank Linkage Program

Years	MFI-Bank Linkage		SHG-Bank Linkage	
	Growth	Rank	Growth	Rank
08-09	82.2	15	33.4	12
09-10	102.6	16	23.6	10
10-11	35.3	13	11.4	05
11-12	-16.6	01	16.4	08
12-13	26.0	11	8.4	02
13-14	14.50	07	9.02	03
14-15	36.22	14	20.06	09
15-16	13.69	06	10.81	04
Sum of rank order		83		53
Number of data		8		8
U value		17		
Z value		1.67		

Inference on Hypothesis

The calculated value of U is 18 which is higher than critical value of U (2) at significance level of 0.05 (Table 6). It can be said that the difference in the growth rate of loan outstanding between MFI- Bank linkage and SHG- Bank linkage program is not significant at p = 0.05. It is further confirmed by calculating Z score (1.67) which is less than 1.96. There is no significant difference in the growth rate of loan outstanding between MFI- Bank linkage and SHG- Bank linkage program in India is upheld.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, both the bank linkage programs are important for alleviation of poverty and growth of the economy. Table 2 shows that The CAGR of amount of loan disbursed to MFI during the period from 2007-08 to 2015-16 is 33.56 percent while the CAGR of total amount of loan disbursed to SHGs in India for the same period is 17.33 percent. Thus, it discloses that the average growth of MFI-bank linkage is impressive which is double than SHG- bank linkage program. But hypothesis testing proves that there is no significant difference in the growth rate of loan disbursement between MFI- Bank linkage and SHG-Bank Linkage program, so null hypothesis is upheld. Table 5 reveals that the CAGR of amount of loan outstanding against MFI during the period from 2007-08 to 2015-16 is 32.07 percent while the CAGR of total amount of loan outstanding against SHGs in India for the period is 14.41 percent. Thus, it discloses that the average growth of MFI- bank linkage is good as compared to SHG-bank linkage program. But hypothesis testing proves that there is no significant difference in the growth rate of loan outstanding between MFI- Bank linkage and SHG-Bank Linkage program, so null hypothesis is upheld.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The present study has certain limitation. It fully relies on the secondary data provided in website. Thus, the figures of secondary data have bearing on the outcome of the study. Moreover, the study is limited to the period of eight years only.

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